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Empirical Test of Modigliani and Miller Irrelevant Capital Structure Hypothesis in Nigeria Financial Market

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ABSTRACT

This study tested the irrelevant capital structure hypothesis of Modigliani and Miller using panel data of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The estimated regression model found that is capital structure explained 66 percent variation on the firm value of the quoted firms. From the findings, the study conclude that capital structure is relevant, this confirm to the Gordon capital structure relevant opinion as oppose the MM hypothesis. the study recommend that policies should be made to enhance optimal capital structure of the quoted firms for better capital structure policy and management of the quoted firms and the regulatory authority should manage external forces such as global financial crises that affects optimal capital structure policies. The regulatory bodies should device policies that help create conducive environments that will enhance optimal capital structure of quoted firms.

Keywords: Modigliani and Miller, Irrelevant Capital Structure Hypothesis, Nigeria Financial Market

INTRODUCTION

Modigliani and Miller (MM) 1958 illustrated that under certain key assumptions, firm's value is unaffected by its capital structure. Capital market is assumed to be perfect in Modigliani and Miller's world, where insiders and outsiders have free access to information; no transaction cost, bankruptcy cost and no taxation exist; equity and debt choice become irrelevant and internal and external funds can be perfectly substituted. The M-M theory (1958) argues that the value of a firm should not depend on its capital structure. The theory argued further that a firm should have the same market value and the same Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) at all capital structure levels because the value of a company should depend on the return and risks of its operation and not on the way it finances those operations. Miller brought forward the next version of irrelevance theory of capital structure. He appealed that, capital structure decisions of firms with both corporate and personal taxes circumstances are irrelevant (Miller, 1977, Osayande, & Orobator, 2024; Usman & Jimba, 2024).

There are two main schools of thoughts in the area of capital structure theory; these are the traditional and the irrelevancy theories. While the traditional theory whose major proponent includes Durand (1952, 1959) believed that the overall market value of the firm is determined by its capital structure; but Modigliani and Miller (1958) argued otherwise. This off course ushers in the modern theory of capital structure which began with their famous proposition describing the conditions of capital structure irrelevant. According to the theory, the overall market value of a firm is not affected by the capital structure employed, rather it is purely independent because, managers do have access to financial markets and the same applies to companies and investors which position them for homemade advantage. This view was also corroborated by Luigi and Sorin (2011).

The value of a firm is the sum total of equity and debt, it is determined on the basis of book value or market value. It is the value of its assets plus the value of tax benefits enjoyed as a result of debt minus the value of bankruptcy cost associated with debt. It refers to the sum of its debt and equity and this depends only on the income stream generated by its assets. Pandey (2004) opined that the value of a firm is the sum of the values of all its securities which is the sum of its equity and debt. The value of the firm's equity is the discounted value of its shareholders earnings called net income. Debt is value reducing for high growth firms and it is value enhancing for low-growth firms. There are two forms of capital which are equity and debt capital. Miller (1958) stated that firm value is determined by company's asset earnings power and not by capital structure. The positive effect of asset earnings power implies that if the company has higher earning powers, then the asset turnover will be more efficient which will affect corporate value.

There have been age-long divergences among scholars on the effect of capital structure and firm value. The Modigliani and Miller theory, proposed by Modigliani and Miller (1958 and 1963), forms the basis for modern thinking on capital structure. In their seminal article, Modigliani and Miller (1958 and 1963) demonstrated that, in a frictionless world, financial leverage is unrelated to firm value, but in a world with tax-deductible interest payments, firm value and capital structure are positively related. Miller (1977) added personal taxes to the analysis and demonstrated that optimal debt usage occurs on a macro level, but it does not exist at the firm level. Interest deductibility at the firm level is offset at the investor level. In addition, Modigliani and Miller (1963) made two propositions under a perfect capital market condition. Their first proposition is that the value of a firm is independent of its capital structure. Their second proposition states that the cost of equity for a leverage firm is equal to the cost of equity for an unleveraged firm plus an added premium for financial risk. However, other theories such as the tradeoff theory (Myers, 1984), pecking order theory (Myers and Majluf, 1984) and agency cost theory (Jensen and Meckling, 1976) argued that if capital structure decision is irrelevant in a perfect market, then, imperfection which exist in the real world may be adduce for its relevance. Such imperfections include bankruptcy costs (Baxter, 1967, Kraus and Litzenberger, 1982; and Kim, 2015; James, 2023), agency cost (Jensen and Meckling, 1976) gains from leverage-induced tax shields (De Angelo and Masulis, 1980) and information asymmetry (Myers, 1984).

Empirical studies (Ogundina and Omah, 2013; Ajao and Osayuwu, 2012; widobie, 2014, Okpara, 2010; Obayagbona and Igbinsosa, 2014) have shown that the Nigeria capital market is not efficient which implies that the assumptions underlying capital structure theories such as the perfect capital market cannot be applied in Nigeria. The assumptions of a perfectly competitive market exclude the impacts of tax, inflation and transaction costs associated with raising money or going bankrupt. This study tested the validity of Modigliani and Miller irrelevant capital structure hypothesis in quoted firms in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Irrelevance Theory of Capital Structure

Modigliani and Miller (1958) propounded the capital structure theory, in the field of investment, where the capital structure represents the mix of debt and equity used by firms to finance long-term investment. Debt is the component of capital loaned by other parties or investors and subject to repayment (Serrasqueiro et al., 2016). Serrasqueiro *et al.*, (2016) examined the capital structure decisions of high-tech SMEs and non-high-tech SMEs in Portugal. The outcome of the study revealed that information asymmetry has an impact on SMEs and creditors on capital structure decisions of service and manufacturing SMEs (Serrasqueiro et al., 2016). Small businesses rely on internal sources for financing business projects (Daskalakis and Psillaki, 2008; Foo, Jamal, Karim, & Ulum, 2015; Serrasqueiro *et al.*, 2016). The internal sources of funding constrain SMEs' ability to finance big projects (Daskalakis and Psillaki, 2008;).

The capital structure theory led the most dominant discourse in corporate finance (Foo et al., 2015; Serrasqueiro et al., 2016). Modigliani and Miller (1958) set the stage for succeeding scholars on investment choices where current markets are immaterial (Serrasqueiro et al., 2016). The capital structure

theory led to vigorous debates in areas of corporate finance and academics (Serrasqueiro et al., 2016). Despite the diversity of the capital structure literature, relatively few scholars have explored the financing decisions of SMEs (Foo et al., 2015; Serrasqueiro et al., 2016).

Most of these researchers have ignored the uniqueness of SMEs, which represent most of activities contributing to gross domestic product (GDP) and employment in most countries (Foo et al., 2015). One possible explanation for the limited research is that SME data are often insufficient and sometimes inaccurate because of private ownership, and owners may not disclose information (Foo et al., 2015; Serrasqueiro et al., 2016). The proponents of the capital structure theory simplified the procedure for companies but did not adequately describe the opportunities available to small businesses, thereby offering limited advice on capital choices to small enterprises (Foo et al., 2015; Serrasqueiro et al., 2016).

The main propositions of the MM theorem are:

- **Proposition I:** the market value of any firm is independent of its capital structure.
- **Proposition II:** the rate of return on equity grows linearly with the debt ratio.
- **Proposition III:** the market value of any firm is independent of its dividend policy.

Proposition I: The Irrelevance of Capital Structure

The MM theorem demonstrates that in a perfect market firms cannot benefit from changes in their capital structure. It is assumed that:

- 1) Two identical companies choose a different capital structure;
- 2) There are only two ways of financing the business: either through equity or bond issuance;
- 3) The cost of borrowing money is the same for individual investors and companies;
- 4) Profits are perpetuities, as firms do not invest;
- 5) Information is perfect and costless;
- 6) There are no transaction costs or income taxes;
- 7) Agency costs are not considered, thus there is no conflict of interest between management and shareholders.

To better understand the theorem, the following demonstration assumes that the firm pays a proportional τ income tax. In fact, corporate taxation was introduced in a second version of the theorem, which was published in 1963.

To obtain the market value of the *unlevered firm* (U) – i.e. the firm which finances itself with equity only – one of the alternatives is to start from its net income, which is:

$$EBIt(1 - \tau) \tag{1}$$

From equation (3) it is possible to determine the firm’s cash flow by adding the depreciation (*Dep*) accumulated in the same accounting period. According to the hypotheses, the firm does not make any new investment other than replacing the consumed assets, thus the investment (*I*) is equal to the depreciation. The free cash flow of the unlevered company (*FCF_U*) will then be:

$$FCF_U = EBIT(1 - \tau) + Dep - I = EBIT(1 - \tau) \tag{2}$$

This result demonstrates that when considering cash flows as perpetuities, the *FCFU* is equal to the firm’s *EBIT* after taxes. If the cost of capital of the unlevered firm is defined as *k_o*, the company’s present value will be:

$$V_U = \frac{FCF_U}{k_o} = \frac{EBIT(1 - \tau)}{k_o} \tag{3}$$

To calculate the value of the *levered firm* (L) – i.e. the firm which uses both debt and equity to finance its operations – it is necessary to identify the remuneration of both shareholders and bondholders. The cash flow attributable to the first group consists on the net profit (*P*) plus depreciation (*Dep*) minus the investments (*I*), while the remuneration to the second group is the bonds’ interest rate (*kd*). The total free cash flow for the levered company (*FCFL*) is:

$$FCF_L = NP + Dep - 1 + k_d D = (EBIT - k_d D)(1 - \tau) + Dep - 1 + k_d D \quad (4)$$

$$FCF_L = EBIT(1 - \tau) + \tau k_d D$$

The first addendum of equation (6) is the cash flow generated by the unlevered firm. It is assumed that the risk for this component is the same for both companies (levered and unlevered) so its cost of capital will be equal to k_o . The second addendum embodies the tax shield which arises from the use of debt. As long as the company's profits remain constant over the years, it is possible to assume that the tax shield has the same risk as bonds' interest rate (k_d). The levered company's present value will then be:

$$V_L = \frac{EBIT(1 - \tau)}{k_o} + \frac{\tau k_d D}{k_d} = \frac{EBIT(1 - \tau)}{k_o} + \tau D \quad (5)$$

$$V_L = V_u + \tau D$$

The levered firm's value is equal to the unlevered firm's value plus the present value of the tax shield. However, the original MM theorem does not include any market imperfections nor taxes ($\tau = 0$), therefore the proposition I of MM states that:

$$V_L = V_u \quad (6)$$

Proposition II: The Rate of Return on Equity

The proposition II of MM states that the rate of return on equity grows linearly with the debt ratio, as the equity risk increases with the increase of debt. According to the proposition I (when taxes are considered), it is possible to write the levered firm's balance sheet as:

V_u (unlevered firm's value)	D (debt / bonds)
τD (tax shield)	E (equity)

The unlevered firm's value does not include the benefit of financial leverage. When debt is increased to D , the firm value increases by τD . The expected cash flow from the left part of the balance sheet can be written as:

$$V_u k_o + \tau k_d D \quad (7)$$

As there is a risk connected to the firm's real activities, their expected return is k_o . The tax shield has the same risk as the debt, thus its expected return is k_d .

The expected cash flow for the bondholders and shareholders together is:

$$k_d D + k_e E \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) demonstrates that the expected return on equity is k_e , whereas the expected return on debt is equal to k_d . Since the model assumes that earnings are perpetuities and that there is no growth, flow to equity is entirely distributed as dividends. Consequently, (8) is equal to (9).

$$k_d D + k_e E = V_u k_o + \tau k_d D \quad (9)$$

Dividing both sides of equation (9) by E , subtracting $k_d D$ from sides and reorganizing, the result is:

$$k_e = \frac{V_u}{E} k_o - (1 - \tau) \frac{D}{E} k_d \quad (10)$$

Since the levered firm's value (V_L) is equal to $V_u + \tau D = D + E$, the unlevered firm's value is equal to $V_u = E + (1 - \tau) D$. As a result, the equation (10) can be written as:

$$k_e = \frac{E + (1 - \tau) D}{E} k_o - (1 - \tau) \frac{D}{E} k_d \quad (11)$$

Collecting the terms with $(1 - \tau) \times (D / E)$, we obtain the equation (11) which is the proposition II of MM theorem:

$$k_e = k_o + \frac{D}{E}(1 - \tau)(k_o - k_d) \tag{12}$$

When $\tau = 0$, the rate of return on equity of a levered company is equal to the rate of return on an unlevered firm's equity (k_o) plus a risk premium which depends on the company's debt ratio. Higher the debt ratio implies higher the risk to the firm's shareholders, as their residual rights on the company's assets is subordinated to the right of debt owners to be paid before everybody else. Hence, the k_e required by the shareholders will also be higher.

If taxation is considered, there are some interesting implications. To understand them better, it is necessary to define the *wacc* (weighted average cost of capital), i.e. the rate that the firm is expected to pay on average to all its security holders to finance its assets. If $\tau = 0$, The *wacc* will be:

$$wacc = \frac{D}{D + E}k_d + \frac{E}{D + E}k_e \tag{13}$$

In a perfect market, the *WACC* is constant, and it is always equal to k_o . The equation (13) therefore confirms what said so far: the rate of return on the investment k_o does not change after an alteration of the capital structure. This result does not hold when taxation is included. As the debt is tax-advantaged if compared to equity, it is possible to demonstrate that the *WACC* of a levered firm declines with the increase of the debt ratio in a world with corporate taxation.

$$wacc = \frac{D}{D + E}k_d(1 - \tau) + \frac{E}{D + E}k_e \tag{14}$$

As debt is usually cheaper than equity, the theorem states that in a world with corporate taxation, an optimal capital structure does exist, and it is made by 100% of debt (and consequently 0% of equity).

Figure 1 summarizes the results of MM theorem's proposition II. The financial leverage increases the risk for the shareholders, thus the cost of equity (k_e) increases to compensate the higher risk. If taxation is not considered, the *WACC* is not affected by the financial leverage, and it is equal to the cost of capital of the unlevered firm (k_o). However, if taxes are included, the firm can benefit from the tax shield when increasing its debt to equity ratio, and the *WACC* decreases as a result while the *WACC* is a continuous line, the k_o is represented by a single dot in the graph.

Figure 1: Cost of capital according to the MM theorem

Neoclassical Theory of Investment

The Neoclassical theory of investment could be based on the optimal capital accumulation (Jorgenson, 1963). Neoclassical theory of investment is based on the assumption of profit maximizing behavior by firms (Samuel, 1996) and the assumption that the management seeks to maximize the present net worth of the firm. Hence, an investment project should be undertaken if and only if it increased the value of the shares (Tobin, 1969, Yoshikawa, 1980). Danielson and Scott (2006) put it clear that, the firms will make set of investments decisions that will maximize shareholders wealth. Hence, the rule is invest in all positive net present value projects and reject those with a negative net present value. The neoclassical model of optimal capital accumulation may be derived by maximizing present value of the firm, by maximizing the integral of discounted profits of the firm, or simply by maximizing profit at each point of time (Jorgenson, 1967; Eklund, 2013). There are two assumptions regarding the theory of investment decisions as highlighted by Danielson and Scott (2006), first, the primary goal of a firm's shareholder is to maximize firm value; second, a firm has access to perfect financial markets allowing it to finance all value enhancing projects. A number of investment criteria can be used by businesses when making investment decisions. These criteria may be grouped into two; Discounted cash flow criteria and Non-discounted cash flow criteria (Pandey, 1976). Under the discounted cash flow criteria there are the following methods: Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Modified Internal Rate of Return (MIRR), and Profitability Index. While under the non-discounted cash flow methods are as follows; Pay Back (PB) and Accounting Rate of Return (ARR).

Tobin's Q Theory of Investment

This Theory relates to the rate of investment as a function of Q, where Q is the ratio of the market value of new additional investment goods to their replacement cost (Tobin, 1969). If investors value assets at prices which are greater than replacement costs, then there are strong inducements for investment in reproducible real capital (Ciccolo, *et al.*, 1979). This theory was in sharp contrast to the output-oriented models like neoclassical model and acceleration model in that it attempted to explain investment on a financial basis in terms of portfolio balance; this translates to the concept based on the q ratio; that is the ratio of the market value of capital to its replacement cost. Grunfeld (1960) proposed the use of the firm's market value as proxy for potential investment undertakings and further stated that investment depends on the market value of the firm in a direct correlated way, this approach to investment being influenced by the market value of the firm can be seen as a relation to Tobin's Q theory. While the accelerator, neoclassical, modified neoclassical, and the cash flow models do not explicitly consider the optimal adjustment path for the firm's capital stock when it is away from that level, the Q theory characterizes the complete evolution of the capital stock from the underlying optimization problem of investments differ from the preceding investment models such as the accelerator models and Jorgenson's model in that it is not output-based. In contrast, investment is thus not viewed as a function of output as in the previous models, but instead assumed to be determined by the firm's market value (Karin, *et al.* 2008). The contrast is also elaborated by (Clark, 1979) where he states that the Q models should not be viewed as complements but rather substitutes to the standard neoclassical models.

Capital Structure

Capital structure refers to the different options used by firm in financing its assets (Bhaduri, 2002). Generally, a firm can go for different levels/mixes of debts, equity, or other financial arrangements. The foundation for theories and research focus on the subject of capital structure began with the introduction of Modigliani and Miller's (M&M) theoretical model about corporate capital structure in 1958 which is considered to have created the turning point for modern corporate finance theory. The theory provides insight into a firm's capital structure decision in a capital market free of taxes, transaction costs, and other frictions. Following Modigliani and Miller (1958), most theories such as the Pecking Order Theory, Agency Theory and Trade off Theory have sought to explain capital structure by introducing frictions omitted in the original Modigliani and Miller framework.

According to Myers (2001) there is no universal theory of the debt-equity choice, and no reason to expect one. However, there are several useful theories as identified earlier each of which helps to understand the debt-to-equity structure that firms choose. These theories can be divided into two groups -either they predict the existence of the optimal debt-equity ratio for each firm (so-called static trade-off models) or they declare that there is no well-defined target capital structure (pecking-order hypothesis).

Static trade-off models understand the optimal capital structure is achieved when the marginal present value of the tax shield on additional debt is equal to the marginal present value of the costs of financial distress on additional debt. On the other hand, the pecking-order theory suggests that there is no optimal capital structure but firms ration between internal financing (retained earnings) to external funds depending on the extent of perceived information asymmetry in the financing environment. A number of factors may influence the financial structure of companies. Salawu (2007) identified factors such as ownership structure and management control, growth, profitability, issuing cost, and tax issues associated with debt as the major factors influencing bank's capital structure. Bevan and Danbolt (2001) highlighted company size, profitability, tangibility, growth opportunities, non-debt tax shields and dividend as possible determinants of the capital structure choice.

Equity Capital

Pandey (1999) defined equity capital as including share-capital, share premium, reserves and surpluses (retained earnings). Typically, equity capital consists of two types which include: contributed capital, which is the money that was originally invested in the business in exchange for shares of stock or ownership and retained earnings, which represents profits from past years that have been kept by the company and used to strengthen the statement of financial position or fund growth, acquisitions, or expansion. Generally, equity strategies are defined as dividend cuts or omissions and equity issues. Firms mostly accept this solution to maintain liquidity to conserve for debt obligations as well as raising funds in purpose of new investment and increase working capital.

Equity finance refers to the sale of an ownership interest to raise funds for business purposes. In order to grow, any company will face the need for additional capital, which it may try to obtain through debt or equity. If the company opts for equity, the owner sells a stake to others. During early growth stages of Company, especially when the company does not have sufficient equity financing can provide capital from investors who are willing to take risks along with the entrepreneur (Berger & Udell, 1998). Similarly, when accompany has prospects of explosive growth, it can raise substantial capital through equity financing. Various types of equity financing are available.

Equity investors may combine equity with convertible debt or straight debt. This is done either as a form of extended due diligence, or to meet cash flow requirements while limiting dilution of the principal owner's shareholding. Equity finance represents ownership capital, as equity shareholders collectively own the company. They enjoy the rewards in the form of residual dividends as well as bear the risks of ownership. However, their liability is limited to their capital contributions.

With reference to a firm with performance or financial distress, a cutting dividend or dividend omission is normally executed. Another aspect of capital structure is for companies to buy back previously issued equity using debt financing. This would be accomplished by taking out a business, commercial, or bank loan in the amount of the equity buyback. In some cases, a company may have a capital structure heavily weighted towards equity. In such cases, buying back previously issued stock and substituting bank loans or other debt financing can optimize the capital structure resulting in a lower overall cost of capital.

Equity unlike long-term debt includes paid-up capital, share-premium, reserves and surplus or retained earnings. Igben (2004) defines paid-up capital as the portion of called-up capital which has been paid-up by shareholders. He defined reserves as the amount set aside out of profit earned by the company, which are not designed to meet any liability, contingency, commitment or reduction in value of assets known to exist in the balance sheet. Furthermore, reserves may be voluntarily created by directors or statutorily required by law. Share premium is the excess amount derived from the issue of shares at a price that is above its par value. And finally, retained earnings are profit invested back into the business in order to create more resources for operations and invariably increase the value of the firm.

Debt Capital

The debt capital in a firm's capital structure refers to the long-term bonds the firm use in financing its investment decisions because the firm has years, if not decades, to come up with the principal, while paying interest only in the meantime. The cost of debt capital in the capital structure depends on the health of the firm's statement of financial position. Debt restructuring refers to a firm changing its debt structure by either increasing or decreasing leverage. In practice, borrowers might make more new loan contracts (increase leverage) or renew debt. Debt restructuring usually means the injection of high levels of debt to increase the leverage of the company and thereby reduces the likelihood that the firm will be a takeover candidate (Rock and Rock, 1990).

A firm decides to negotiate creditors for interest lowering or maturity extent (Sudarsanam and Lai, 2001; Kam, Citron, and Muradoglu, 2008; Yawson, 2008). Debt can be restructured to benefit the business by refinancing existing loans or obtaining new ones secured by real property, equipment, receivables or in select cases, future cash flows. This process effectively reduces the cost of the debt in the long term and increases cash flow for the business. The increased cash flow can be reinvested in the company in a variety of ways that influence growth for the future. If an influx of capital is needed, a new commercial or business loan can provide for growth. This is considered capital restructuring as new leveraged debt capital is added to the company balance sheet.

Empirical Review

Osayande and Orobator, (2024) empirically tested the Modigliani-Miller capital structure of Irrelevance theory, using listed nonfinancial firms in Ghana. The study employed the ex-post facto research design, and secondary data retrieved from annual reports of listed non-financial firms in Ghanaian Stock Exchange was utilized. The population of the study comprised all non-financial firms in Ghana, while the sample of the study was made up of fifteen (15) quoted non-financial firms in Ghana. The scope of the study spans from 2010 to 2019. The panel regression technique was used for the estimation of the model specified for the study. The results for the test of Modigliani- Miller (1958) theory (MM proposition without taxes) revealed that, the overall results support the Modigliani- Miller-I theory without corporate taxes. On the other hand, testing the MM (1963) adjusted theory with the incorporation of taxes, the study also validates the MM-2 proposition with taxes. The study therefore recommends that, companies should alter their capital structure composition and take advantages of income-saving benefits from debt, which can free up income and hence improve firm value.

James (2023) tested the dividend clientele hypothesis of Modigliani and Miller using panel data of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The purpose was to investigate how dividend clientele effect relates to share prices. The estimated regression model found that changes in dividend payout ratio, retained earnings and tax explained 73.9 percent variation in stock prices of the quoted manufacturing firms. Correlation and multiple regressions were used to test the relationship between variables. Cross sectional data were sourced from financial statement and annual reports of the firms. Based on the analysis of fixed and random effect results, fixed effect was used. From the findings, the study concludes that variation in dividend payout ratio, retained earnings and income tax positively affects the stock prices of the quoted manufacturing firms. The study recommends that relevant authorities should ensure dividend policy framework that will positively affects the share prices of the quoted manufacturing firms.

Usman and Jimba (2024) tested dividend irrelevance theory: evidence from Nigeria's non-finance listed firms. The paper reviews related concepts, a few theories, and empirical to explore dividend mechanisms, analysis, and impact on a firm's growth. Secondary data was retrieved from annual reports of fifteen (15) non-finance listed firms in the Nigeria Stock Exchange (officially Nigeria Exchange Group; during the fiscal periods of 2010 to 2022). A judgmental research sampling design was adopted to assess the variables using a panel data regression technique via Ordinary Least Square model, to estimate the specified equation. To observe the relationship between the dependent (explained); Dividend Payout (DIP) and selected independent (explanatory) variables; Earnings Yield of Firms Value (EYV) Data, Aggregate Asset Share prices (ASP) of firms, Market Value Added Firm Value (MVAA), Tobin

Performance Data (TOBQ) and Price to Revenue Firm Valuation (PRV). Prob (Fstat.) at 0.000 proves that the logged exogenous variables are significant. T-statistic values show that logmarket value (0.000000) logearnings yield (eyv; -5.45), logprv (-0.504126), and logtobq (0.000000) are insignificant (at 5%). Interestingly, the R-squared and the Adjusted R-squared result of the logged independent variables both present a 100% estimate, depicting significance in the regressed model. However, policy implications and recommendations are anchored on the need to practically improve non-finance listed firms in the NSE by addressing the problems of agency cost, high tax rates on dividends, insider-information factors, unaccountable dividend payouts, balance sheet discrepancies amongst other macro-economic indicators that can threaten the development of non-finance quoted firms. All hands (researchers, analysts, policymakers) must be on deck in the areas of share price reactions, market base and performance as well as the under-development of the stock market as arguments of dividend irrelevance will remain a puzzle in the long run be it accepted or rejected.

Lucky and Onyinyechi (2019) tested Miller and Modigliani dividend policy irrelevant hypothesis in Nigeria. The objective was to examine the validity of the irrelevant hypothesis. Tobins Q measure of market value was modeled as the function of dividend payout ratio, retention ratio, dividend per share and dividend yield. 20 firms were selected on the basis of availability of information necessary for conducting the study and the readiness of annual financial reports for the period of 10 years from 2008-2017. Cross sectional data was sourced from financial statement and annual reports of the firms. Based on the analysis of fixed and random effect results, random effect was used. The study revealed that 75 percent variation on the market value can be predicted by variation on independent variables in the regression model. The beta coefficient of the variables found that all the independent variables have positive and significant relationship with market value of the selected quoted firms. The study concludes that dividend policy is relevant as oppose to the irrelevant hypothesis of Miller and Modigliani. Its therefore recommend that managers should manage their dividend policies effectively since it is relevant and has significant effect on market value and optimal dividend policy which implies policy of trade-off between dividend payout and retain earnings should be well managed and investors should have adequate knowledge of dividend policy of quoted firms that will correspond with their investment objectives of avoid conflict in dividend policy.

Adesola and Okwong (2009) tested the relevance of Nigeria stock price dividend theories with cross-sectional data from twenty-seven companies over the period 1996-2006. They commented that they have discovered the positive and significant impact of dividends on stock prices. The A-sample activities of Nigerian companies indirectly call into question the empirical validity of the dividend insignificance. Khalid, Chijioke and Aruoriwo (2010) investigated the effect of dividend yield and dividend payout ratio on changes in UK listed companies stock prices. A regression model was used to analyze the data, which showed a positive relationship between dividend yield and stock prices and showed that dividend payouts are statistically insignificant.

Amadasun (2011) tried to test the hypothesis that dividend would not increase the price of Nigerian equities using First Bank (Nig) plc as a case study. The study used a regression model that included share price per share as the explanatory variables, earnings per share, return on capital employed, retained earnings, and price-earnings ratio. The results of the study showed a statistically insignificant regression coefficient for both per-share dividend and earnings per share.

Toby (2014) investigated the importance of dividend policy in determining the price of Nigerian stock market stock by selecting a couple of dozen shares between 2005 and 2012, along with a dividend regression analysis and timing of retained earnings in individual companies. The study found that there is no significant relationship between the change in dividend policy and the change in share price. This surprising result differs from the existing literature on the effect of dividends on stock prices. The result was company-by-company analysis (separate regression analysis for each sample), rather than using panel or cross-sectional data to reflect differences between firms. In addition, the study did not include a well-defined income variable in its analysis. Instead, he used retained earnings. The results showed that dividend and retained earnings were not a statistically significant determinant of share price. The study

conclude that the results are in line with previous research stating that dividend policy is irrelevant in determining the value of the company is therefore highly dubious and invalid.

Udobi and Iyiegbuniwe (2018) examined the impact of current dividend on market shares prices of the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study analyzed fifteen years (15) secondary data of NSE quoted firms with mediation analysis. Stock prices is the dependent variable while current dividend, current earnings, Asset-growth, sales-growth, insider-shareholding and Leverage are the independent variables. The findings indicate that current dividend has a direct (Unique) effect on share price, and at the same time has indirect effect on share price through current earnings. It concluded that current earnings partially mediate the effect of current dividend on quoted Nigerian firms.

Vasiliou and Eriotis (2003) tested the Lintner model and concluded that there are two ways to improve the original model; For the purpose of treating the change in the dividend between t and t-1 as dependent variables and independent variables, the change in the profit of the enterprise between t and t-1 and the change in the dividend between t-1 shall be taken into account. 1yacht -2. Vasiliou and Eriotis believe that Greek companies adopt dividend payments such as dividend payments, depending on the long-term goal of dividend payments (denoted by the dividend variable delay) which is adjusted accordingly to net income.

Literature Gap

The empirical studies examined in this study focused on the test of dividend irrelevant theory of Modigliani and Miller in 1958. There is no study on the test of MM capital structure irrelevant hypothesis most especially the developing financial market like Nigeria where the applications of the MM assumption is more difficult. This study therefore tested the irrelevant capital structure hypothesis in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study used quasi experimental research design approach to test the validity of MM hypothesis on irrelevance of capital structure in Nigeria. This approach combines theoretical consideration (a-priori criterion) with the empirical observation and extract maximum information from the available data. The researcher's aim in this study is to ascertain whether capital structure is irrelevant in Nigeria as proposed by Miller and Modigliani in 1959. The study used secondary sourced from Nigerian Stock Exchange Factsheet and annual reports and statement of accounts of 22 manufacturing firms classified as consumer goods manufacturing firms.

Analytical Framework and Empirical Model Specification

This analysis is carried out within a panel data estimation framework. The preference of this estimation method is not only because it enables a cross-sectional time series analysis which usually makes provision for broader set of data points, but also because of its ability to control for heterogeneity and endogeneity issues. Hence panel data estimation allows for the control of individual-specific effects usually unobservable which may be correlated with other explanatory variables included in the specification of the relationship between dependent and explanatory variables (Hausman and Taylor, 1981). The basic framework for panel data regression takes the form:

$$Y_{it} = \beta X'_{it} + \alpha Z'_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (15)$$

Where:

- Y = dependent variable
- D = independent variable
- β_o = intercept
- β_i = coefficient of the explanatory variable
- e = error term
- I = cross-sectional variable
- T = time series variable

In the equation above, the heterogeneity or individual effect is Z^i which may represent a constant term and a set of observable and unobservable variables. When the individual effect Z_i contains only a constant term, OLS estimation provides a consistent and efficient estimates of the underlying parameters (Kyereboah-Coleman, 2007); hut if Z_i is un-observable and correlated with X_{it} , then emerges the need to use other estimation method because OLS will give rise to biased and inconsistent estimates.

Similarly for endogeneity issues, it is generally assumed that the explanatory variables located on the right hand side of the regression equation are statistically independent of the disturbance ε_{it} such that the disturbance term ε_{it} is assumed to be uncorrelated with columns of the parameters X_{it} and Z_{it} as stated in equation (1), and has zero mean and constant variance $\sigma^2\eta$ (Hausman and Taylor, 198). If this assumption is violated, then OLS estimation will yield biased estimates of the underlying parameters of β (Mayston, 2002). Hence, endogeneity problems arise when the explanatory variables are correlated with the disturbance term ε_{it} (Mayston, 2002; Hausman and Taylor, 1981). In order to circumvent these problems, panel estimation techniques of fixed and random effects will be adopted in this study, in addition to the traditional pooled regression estimation. Decisions were made between the fixed and random effect models using the Hausman specification test. The panel model for the study is specified base on the modified model of Akeem, Edwin, Kiyanjui and Kayode (2014).

Model Specification

Pooled Regression Specification

$$FV_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ECR_{1it} + \alpha_2 DCR_{2it} + DER_{3it} + \varepsilon_{1it} \quad (16)$$

Fixed Effect Model Specification

$$FV_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ECR_{1it} + \alpha_2 DCR_{2it} + DER_{3it} + \sum_i^9 \alpha_i idum + \varepsilon_{1it} \quad (17)$$

Random Effect Model Specification

$$FV_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ECR_{1it} + \alpha_2 DCR_{2it} + \alpha_3 DER_{3it} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{1it} \quad (18)$$

Where

FV = Firm value measured by market value of the quoted firms

ECR = Equity capital ratio measured as percentage of equity capital to total capital

DCR = Debt capital ratio measured as percentage of debt capital to total capital

DER = Debt equity ratio measured as percentage debt to total equity

ε_{it} = Stochastic or disturbance/error term.

t = Time dimension of the variables

α_0 = Constant or intercept.

A-Priori Expectation

Base on theories such as market efficiency theory and empirical results examined in this study, the variables are expected to have a positive effect on the dependent variables. The mathematical implication is stated as follows:

$1 \beta > 1 \beta > 1 \beta > 1 \beta > 0$ Reject MM hypothesis

$1 \beta < 1 \beta < 1 \beta < 1 \beta > 0$ Accept MM hypothesis

$1 t > 1 t > 1 t > 1 t > 0$ Reject MM hypothesis

$1 t < 1 t > 1 t > 1 t > 0$ Accept MM hypothesis

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The objective of the study as earlier stated was to the validity of MM capital structure irrelevant hypothesis in among Nigeria quoted manufacturing firms.

Table 1: Panel Unit Roots Tests

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross sections	Obs	Order of int	Remark	Decision
FV							
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-16.1981	0.0000	21	168	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.10892	0.0009	21	168	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	61.6712	0.0255	21	168	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
PP - Fisher Chi-square	128.455	0.0000	21	189	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
ECR							
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-11.9105	0.0000	22	132	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-7.58558	0.0000	22	132	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	141.448	0.0000	22	132	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
PP - Fisher Chi-square	255.244	0.0000	22	154	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
DCR							
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-2.93589	0.0017	22	154	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.69266	0.0001	22	154	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	95.8312	0.0000	22	154	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
PP - Fisher Chi-square	260.927	0.0000	22	176	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
DER							
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-5.33942	0.0000	21	126	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-4.67457	0.0000	20	120	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	101.584	0.0000	20	120	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0
PP - Fisher Chi-square	284.497	0.0000	20	140	1(I)	Stationary	Reject H0

Source: computed from E-view 12.0

* Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality, Im, Pesaran and Shin; ADF - Fisher and PP - Fisher - Null Hypothesis: Unit Root (Individual Unit Root process). Levin, Lin & Chu Test.

- Null Hypothesis: Unit Root (common Unit Root process), Automatic lag length selection based on Modified Schwarz Criteria and Bartlett kernel.

It can be seen from the Table 1 that the data are stationary at first difference for 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance. It is therefore deduced that the series are characterized as I (1) process; consequently, suitable for a use in a test for panel cointegration between agency problem and market value of the consumer goods manufacturing firms.

Table 2: Short Run Regression Results

Variable	Pooled Effect			Fixed effect			Random effect		
	β coefficient	T. stat	p. value	β coefficient	T. stat	p. value	β coefficient	T. stat	p. value
ECR	0.076096	1.071826	0.2850	0.001769	2.010999	0.9912	0.930934	3.338186	0.0006
DCR	0.007372	2.247872	0.0045	0.015003	2.517818	0.0052	1.012805	3.451799	0.0000
DER	0.288877	4.118455	0.0001	0.296452	2.775688	0.0060	0.892226	3.340487	0.0010
C	2.891650	5.323702	0.0000	3.157678	3.967741	0.0001	3.067364	4.567434	0.0000
R ²	0.096522			0.339696			0.660102		
AdjR ²	0.079713			0.254605			0.542616		
F-stat	5.742305			3.992164			3.437066		
F- Prob	0.000208			0.000000			0.009527		
D W	0.939339			1.159768			1.902271		
Hausman Test									
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic			Chi-Sq. d.f		Prob.			
Cross-section random	1.996771			4		0.7364			

Source: computed from E-view 12.0

Analysis of Results

Given that the Chi-Sq. Probability is greater than 0.05, being 0.7346, the random effect model is adopted. As regards the model summary, the R^2 in the random effects model is 0.66 implying that capital structure accounts for approximately 66% variation in firm value of quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The adjusted R^2 also shows 0.542616 implying that irrespective of the number of endogenous variables, capital structure would not account for more than 54% variation in firm value of the selected companies. The Durbin Watson is 1.902271 as computed from the random effect results at 5% level of significance with four explanatory variables and 220 observations. This is greater than the calculated DW for dL and du which are 0.861 and 1.562 respectively. Besides, given that it revolves around 2, it is permissible; therefore, there is no evidence of autocorrelation. It is further seen that the constant of the model is 3.067364, implying that if the endogenous variables are held constant or unchanged; the exogenous variable - firm value will be elevated by almost 3 units periodically. Comprehensively, the probability of the F-statistics is 0.000000, being less than 0.05; therefore the aggregation of endogenous variables in the model would have a statistically significant relationship with the exogenous variable (firm value).

Table 3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller results (parametric)

Cross ID	AR(1)		Variance	Lag Max lag	Obs
Seven up Bottling Co. Plc	0.302	0.001965	1	--	8
Cadbury Nig. Plc	-0.494	0.034168	1	--	8
Champion Breweries Plc	-0.079	0.026221	1	--	8
Dangote flour plc	-1.219	3.129421	1	--	8
Dangote Sugar RefinPlc	3E-04	0.023074	1	--	8
DN Tyre& Rubber Plc	-0.732	0.001379	1	--	8
Flour Mills	0.355	0.016102	1	--	8
Golden Guinea Brew. Plc	-0.261	0.065285	1	--	8
Guinness Nig. Plc	0.293	0.032867	1	--	8
Honeywell Flour Mills Plc	-0.873	0.034648	1	--	8
Int'l Breweries Plc	-0.579	0.017805	1	--	8
MC Nichols Plc	0.289	9.514749	1	--	8
Mlti-Trex Integrated Food Plc	0.318	0.006884	1	--	8
Northern Nig. Flour Mills Plc	0.338	0.026667	1	--	8
Nascon Allied Ind. Plc	-1.226	0.008638	1	--	8
Nestle Nig. Plc	-0.162	0.004820	1	--	8
Nigerian BrewriesPlc	0.349	0.022188	1	--	8
PZ Cussons Nig. Plc	-0.670	0.005909	1	--	8
UTC Nigeria Plc	0.566	0.008032	1	--	8
Union Dicon Salt Plc	-0.450	0.029087	1	--	8
Unilever Nigeria Plc	-0.091	0.004882	1	--	8
Vita Foam Nigeria Plc	-0.680	0.021999	1	--	8

Source: computed from E-view 12.0

The results of the power for the entire test procedure based on the underlying time series model is stationary as all the procedures produced a reasonably high power over all the sample sizes and order considered except at order 2 where ADF (Augmented Dickey Fuller) produced extremely low power. The power of the tests is extremely high over all the sample sizes and orders considered. From the coefficient of the sample size, most of the firms have linear relationship and also integrated in the order of $I(1)$.

Table 4: Pedroni Residual Cointegration Test

	<u>Statistic</u>	<u>Prob.</u>	<u>WeightedStatistic</u>	<u>Prob.</u>
Panel v-Statistic	-2.928369	0.9983	-3.073093	0.9989
Panel rho-Statistic	4.996743	0.0000	4.331153	0.0000
Panel PP-Statistic	2.369691	0.9911	-0.859390	0.1951
Panel ADF-Statistic	4.466382	0.0000	1.869235	0.9692
	<u>Statistic</u>	<u>Prob.</u>		
Group rho-Statistic	6.241729	0.0000		
Group PP-Statistic	-1.718684	0.0428		
Group ADF-Statistic	3.647105	0.9999		

Source: computed from E-view 12.0

The cointegration test is consistent with Pedroni (2004), which is an Engle-Granger based test. The test allows for heterogeneous intercepts and trend coefficients across cross-sections, with different methods of constructing statistics for testing the null hypothesis of no cointegration. From the results in table 4 it is clear that most of the p-values are all less than 0.05. We can therefore safely conclude that the panel cointegration results provide us with evidence of cointegration since most of Pedroni test statistics reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration for the estimated models.

Table 5: Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

<u>Null Hypothesis:</u>	<u>Obs</u>	<u>F-Statistic</u>	<u>Prob.</u>
ECR does not Granger Cause FV	176	0.68933	0.5033
FV does not Granger Cause ECR		0.01427	0.9858
DCR does not Granger Cause FV	176	0.02672	0.9736
FV does not Granger Cause DCR		0.11040	0.8955
DER does not Granger Cause FV	176	4.29971	0.0151
FV does not Granger Cause DER		1.58992	0.2069

Source: computed from E-view 12.0

Note: ** and *** indicate 5% and 1% significance levels respectively. Lag length is chosen according to the Akaike Information Criterion. For agency cost and market value of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms variable groups Akaike Information Criterion indicates the lag length of zero. To summarize, our Granger causality test results show that there is a uni-directional causal relationship from employee effort to market value of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Analysis of Findings

ECR = 0.930934 > 0 Reject MM Hypothesis

DCR = 1.012805 > 0 Reject MM Hypothesis

DER = 0.892226 > 0 Reject MM Hypothesis

T-test ECR = 0.0006 < 0.05 Significant, Reject MM Hypothesis

T-test DCR = 0.0000 < 0.05 Significant, Reject MM Hypothesis

T-test DER = 0.0010 < 0.05 Significant, Reject MM Hypothesis

Findings of the study proved that capital structure is relevant in Nigeria as oppose the irrelevant theory of Modigliani and Miller in 1958. The findings of this study confirm the findings of Lucky and Onyinyechi (2019) that dividend policy is relevant as oppose to the irrelevant hypothesis of Miller and Modigliani. Adesola and Okwong (2009) commented that they have discovered the positive and significant impact of dividends on stock prices. Amadasun (2011) showed a statistically insignificant regression coefficient for both per-share dividend and earnings per share and Udobi, Iyiegbuniwe & Ezike (2018) that current dividend has a direct (Unique) effect on share price, and at the same time has indirect effect on share price through current earnings.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The argument of Miller and Modigliani (1958) capital structure irrelevance proposition implies that the effect of capital structure on firm value is fully mediated by earnings. This study tested the positions of MM on capital structure irrelevant theory using panel data of quoted firms in Nigeria. The estimated regression model found that there is capital structure explained 66 percent variation on the firm value of the quoted firms. From the findings, the study conclude that capital structure is relevant, this confirm to the Gordon capital structure relevant opinion as oppose the MM hypothesis.

Recommendations

- i. Policies should be made to enhance optimal capital structure of the quoted firms for better dividend policy and positive effect on firm value and policies should be formulated by the management of the quoted firms and the regulatory authority to manage external forces such as global financial crises that affects the capital market and the firm value of the quoted firms.
- ii. The regulatory bodies should device policies that help create conducive environments that will enhance optimal capital structure of quoted firms and Nigerian capital market and the regulators should make policies that will enhance and advance the operation of the capital market for easy source of capital in the financial market.

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